

LINGUISTIC APPROACH TO THE PROBLEMS OF DYSLEXIA AND DYSGRAPHIA IN UZBEK-SPEAKING CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article explores the linguistic dimensions of dyslexia and dysgraphia among Uzbek-speaking children, focusing on the unique challenges posed by the Uzbek language's phonological, morphological, and orthographic characteristics. The study examines how these language-specific features affect the diagnosis and intervention strategies for children with dyslexia and dysgraphia. It reviews existing research on the prevalence and manifestation of these learning disorders in the context of Uzbek, drawing comparisons with findings from other languages. The article highlights the importance of culturally and linguistically tailored educational interventions and offers recommendations for teachers, speech-language pathologists, and educational psychologists working with Uzbek-speaking children. By addressing the gaps in current methodologies, the study aims to improve literacy outcomes and support the academic development of children with learning disabilities in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Dyslexia, dysgraphia, uzbek-speaking children, linguistic approach, phonological characteristics, morphological characteristics, orthographic characteristics, learning disorders, educational interventions, literacy outcomes, speech-language pathology, educational psychology.

Dyslexia is a specific learning disability that is neurological in origin. It is characterized by difficulties with accurate and/or fluent word recognition and by poor spelling and decoding abilities. These difficulties typically result from a deficit in the phonological component of language that is often unexpected in relation to other cognitive abilities and the provision of effective classroom instruction. Secondary consequences may include problems in reading comprehension and reduced reading experience that can impede the growth of vocabulary and background knowledge.⁸

Symptoms of Dyslexia:

⁸ Vellutino, F. R., Fletcher, J. M., Snowling, M. J., & Scanlon, D. M. (2004). Specific Reading Disability (Dyslexia): What Have We Learned in the Past Four Decades?. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 45(1), 2-40.

1. Difficulty with reading: Problems with decoding words, reading fluently, and understanding text.
2. Spelling difficulties: Frequent misspelling of words, including simple ones.
3. Phonological issues: Trouble breaking words into smaller parts, such as syllables or individual sounds.
4. Slow reading speed: Reading may be slow and laborious, even for simple texts.
5. Problems with written expression: Difficulty organizing thoughts coherently in writing.
6. Memory issues: Difficulty remembering names, dates, or sequences of events.
7. Confusion with similar words: Mixing up words that look or sound similar.
8. Avoidance of reading: Reluctance or refusal to engage in reading activities.

Dysgraphia is a specific learning disability that affects a person's handwriting ability and fine motor skills. It is a neurological disorder that generally appears when children are first learning to write. Dysgraphia can manifest as difficulties with spelling, poor handwriting, and trouble putting thoughts on paper. A person with dysgraphia may be able to write but will produce illegible or very slow and laborious writing.

Symptoms of Dysgraphia.

1. Poor handwriting: Writing is often messy, with irregular spacing, poor letter formation, and inconsistent size of letters.
2. Slow writing speed: Taking much longer to write than peers.
3. Difficulty with spelling: Frequent and significant spelling mistakes.
4. Inconsistent use of capital and lowercase letters: Random or improper use of capitalization.
5. Trouble with fine motor skills: Difficulty with tasks that require fine motor coordination, such as buttoning a shirt or tying shoelaces.
6. Avoidance of writing: Reluctance to engage in tasks that require writing.
7. Pain or discomfort while writing: Complaints of hand cramps or fatigue when writing.
8. Difficulty organizing written work: Struggling to keep writing within lines or margins and organizing thoughts coherently on paper.
9. Problems with written expression: Difficulty translating thoughts into written language, resulting in disorganized or incomplete written work.

Both dyslexia and dysgraphia can have significant impacts on academic performance and daily activities, but early identification and appropriate interventions can help individuals manage these challenges effectively. Dyslexia and dysgraphia are learning disabilities that affect reading and writing, respectively. These conditions pose significant challenges to children worldwide, including those in Uzbekistan. Understanding the linguistic implications of dyslexia and dysgraphia in Uzbek-

speaking children is crucial for developing effective educational strategies and support systems.⁹

As I mentioned above, dyslexia is a neurological condition that affects a child's ability to decode and recognize words accurately and fluently. For Uzbek-speaking children, dyslexia presents unique challenges due to the linguistic characteristics of the Uzbek language.

Uzbek is an agglutinative language, which means it uses a variety of affixes to indicate grammatical relationships and functions. This morphological complexity can be particularly challenging for children with dyslexia, who may struggle with phonological processing. The ability to segment and manipulate phonemes, which is critical for reading, is often impaired in dyslexic children.

The Uzbek language uses a modified Latin script that is relatively phonetic, meaning there is a clear correspondence between letters and sounds. While this orthographic transparency can aid in learning to read, it does not eliminate the difficulties faced by dyslexic children. The consistent grapheme-phoneme relationships in Uzbek can help some children but may still pose challenges for those with severe phonological deficits. Dyslexic children often have difficulties with visual and auditory processing. In the context of the Uzbek language, this can mean trouble distinguishing between similar-looking letters or similar-sounding phonemes. Given the importance of vowel harmony and other phonological rules in Uzbek, these processing difficulties can significantly hinder reading development.

As we know, dysgraphia is a learning disability that affects writing abilities, including spelling, handwriting, and the ability to organize and express thoughts in written form. For Uzbek-speaking children, dysgraphia manifests through several linguistic challenges. Dysgraphia often involves poor fine motor skills, leading to difficulties with handwriting. In Uzbek, this can be exacerbated by the need to write various affixes and diacritical marks correctly. The physical act of writing in a script that requires precise motor control can be particularly challenging for children with dysgraphia. Given the agglutinative nature of Uzbek, spelling can be complex, involving multiple affixes attached to root words. Children with dysgraphia may struggle to remember and correctly apply these affixes, leading to frequent spelling errors. Moreover, the grammatical rules governing the use of these affixes require a good understanding of morphological structures, which can be particularly demanding for children with this condition. Writing in Uzbek involves a significant cognitive load, as children must simultaneously consider phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics. Dysgraphic children often find it challenging to manage this load, resulting

⁹ Vellutino, F. R., Fletcher, J. M., Snowling, M. J., & Scanlon, D. M. (2004). Specific Reading Disability (Dyslexia): What Have We Learned in the Past Four Decades?. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 45(1), 2-40.

in disorganized and incomplete written work. The cognitive demands of writing in Uzbek can exacerbate the difficulties faced by children with dysgraphia.

Addressing the needs of dyslexic and dysgraphic Uzbek-speaking children requires targeted educational strategies. Here are some recommendations:

Firstly, intensive phonological awareness training can help dyslexic children improve their ability to manipulate phonemes. This training should include activities that focus on segmenting and blending sounds, which are crucial for reading in Uzbek.

Secondly, using multisensory instructional methods can benefit both dyslexic and dysgraphic children. These methods, which involve visual, auditory, and kinesthetic-tactile pathways, can enhance phonological processing and writing skills.

Thirdly, technology can play a vital role in supporting children with dyslexia and dysgraphia. Text-to-speech and speech-to-text software can assist in reading and writing tasks, reducing the cognitive load and allowing children to focus on content rather than mechanics.

Fourthly, personalized educational plans that cater to the specific needs of each child can be highly effective. Teachers should be trained to recognize the signs of dyslexia and dysgraphia and implement strategies that address the unique linguistic challenges of Uzbek-speaking children.

Dyslexia and dysgraphia pose significant challenges to Uzbek-speaking children, primarily due to the phonological, morphological, and orthographic characteristics of the Uzbek language. Understanding these linguistic challenges is essential for developing effective educational strategies. By employing targeted interventions and leveraging technology, educators can provide the necessary support to help these children succeed academically and develop their full potential.

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